

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMPETENCE IN DESIGNING PEDAGOGICAL
SOFTWARE TOOLS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. This article analyzes the problems related to developing higher education students' competence in designing pedagogical software tools. It also highlights the opportunities for developing students' thinking, creativity, and technological problem-solving competence in the process of designing pedagogical software tools. In addition, the article presents existing problems in developing students' knowledge and skills related to pedagogical software tools.

Keywords: pedagogical software, problem, competence, project, information technologies, programming tools, e-learning, digital technologies, creativity, motivation.

Introduction. Today, due to the rapid digitalization of all spheres of society, there is an increasing need to train highly qualified specialists in the field of information technologies, improve their professional skills, and develop new approaches to teaching disciplines related to this field [1].

At a time when information technologies are rapidly developing, the educational process requires the application of new approaches and methods for designing modern pedagogical software tools. In this regard, teaching pedagogical programming, including the design of pedagogical software tools, through new technologies and methodologies to support students' knowledge and skills in solving pedagogical problems has become one of the most urgent issues.

Designing pedagogical software tools today not only helps students conveniently and intuitively master the basic principles of programming, but also develops their competence in designing pedagogical software tools, creativity, and the ability to solve problems related to pedagogical technologies.

Competence in designing pedagogical software tools is the integration of knowledge, skills, abilities, and personal qualities required to create, develop, implement, and effectively manage software tools used in the educational process.

This competence includes the following key aspects: Pedagogical foundations: knowledge of modern methodologies and principles of organizing the educational process; consideration of students' age, psychological, cognitive, and social characteristics; selection and application of pedagogical approaches aligned with educational goals.

Knowledge and skills in software development: understanding of programming languages, software architecture, and interface design; creation of user-friendly, intuitive, and visually attractive software tools; effective use of multimedia, interactive, and virtual elements.

Didactic requirements and content design: scientific, methodological, and logical structuring of educational materials; ensuring alignment of software tools with educational objectives; focus on developing students' knowledge, skills, and competences.

Innovative technologies and approaches: application of modern educational technologies (such as artificial intelligence, virtual and augmented reality, learning platforms); creating opportunities for individualization and personalization of the learning process.

Assessment, monitoring, and improvement: measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of software tools based on students' knowledge level, motivation, and activity; continuous improvement of software tools based on feedback and results.

Creative approach and teamwork skills: finding innovative and creative solutions in designing pedagogical software tools; effective collaboration with specialists (programmers, educators, designers).

Information security and ethics: ensuring data security when using software tools; compliance with ethical and legal norms in the development of pedagogical software tools.

Analysis of the Literature. Scientific research on developing higher education students' competence in designing pedagogical software tools has been conducted by scholars in our country and CIS countries, including O.A. Shabalina, V.V. Shchukina, E.V. Mikhailova, I.B. Torshina, L.A. Tereshkova, A.Yu. Vasilyeva, A.V. Shcheglov, O.P. Andreeva, Yu.V. Veselova, as well as foreign researchers such as Steven Henderson, Meyerbaum-Salant, and M. Armoni.

In their works, these scholars developed theoretical and methodological strategies for forming students' design skills based on an integrative approach, models for developing project culture among students, organizational and pedagogical foundations of students' design activities, improvement of students' information and communication training in higher education institutions based on computer-aided design tools, and methodologies for developing design skills based on innovative technologies and a creative approach. However, insufficient attention has been paid to developing students' competence specifically in designing pedagogical software tools.

At the same time, in V.T. Juraev's dissertation entitled "Improving the Methodology of Using Pedagogical Software Tools in an E-Learning Environment", the didactic synthesis opportunities of using mobile and SMART technologies in the electronic learning environment were enhanced by prioritizing interactive communication, time control, and presenting information in various forms [2]. In F.B. Turakhonov's research "Improving Practical Physics Lessons in Specialized Schools Based on Pedagogical Software Tools", the stages of improving practical physics lessons were identified based on an integrative approach to the didactic capabilities of organizational and structural components in a modern information-rich educational environment [3].

Although these studies propose theoretical approaches to designing pedagogical software tools, insufficient attention has been given to developing higher education students' competence in this area. Therefore, the proposed research on developing students' competence in designing pedagogical software tools is considered one of the most relevant problems. To conduct research on this issue, it is first necessary to analyze the concepts of competence, pedagogical software tools, and competence in designing pedagogical software tools, as well as researchers' views on these concepts.

According to A. Umarov, "competence is a key characteristic of an individual associated with effective and high performance in the workplace based on processes or situations" [4]. In A.Q. Qunnazarov's study "Improving the Methodology of Using Pedagogical Software Tools in General Secondary Schools (on the Example of Informatics and Information Technologies)", the didactic potential of pedagogical software tools was improved by prioritizing semantic and structural aspects of designing teaching practices based on art design, 3D design, programming languages, and STEAM education criteria [5].

Developing competence in designing pedagogical software tools is the ability to integrate practical knowledge, functional skills, and a creative approach to solving problems, creating projects, modeling

software tools, and analyzing results through the use of pedagogical software tools. Based on this definition, developing higher education students' competence in pedagogical software tools is one of the most important tasks, which determines the relevance of the proposed research.

Research Methodology. Today, shaping students' logical, programming, creative, and cognitive thinking related to designing pedagogical software tools and developing their competence is of great importance. At the same time, pedagogical software tools integrate achievements at each stage of modern digital technology development. Object-oriented approaches, which underlie modern programming technologies, are widely recognized as effective tools for describing processes and phenomena and are commonly used in the development of large-scale software systems.

Z.S. Zhirkova and K.B. Kholikov provided pedagogical definitions of the concept of design [6]. According to Z.S. Zhirkova, "design is a complex task whose solution is carried out by considering the socio-cultural context of the problem and involves the interaction and complementarity of socio-cultural, psychological-pedagogical, technical-technological, and organizational-managerial aspects" [7].

K.B. Kholikov states that "design is an organized system of activities for carrying out complex research and developments that ensure the development and self-development of education as a form of social practice that meets human educational needs" [8].

Based on these definitions and analyses, design can be described as a goal-oriented creative activity involving systematic planning and implementation of ideas, resources, and processes to solve specific problems or create innovations.

Therefore, developing students' competence in designing pedagogical software tools remains one of the most urgent problems. The proposed research aims to address this issue by improving the methodology for developing higher education students' competence in designing pedagogical software tools.

Analysis and Results. The analysis showed that the selected topics provide essential knowledge and skills for developing students' competence in designing pedagogical software tools, namely:

1. Text information processing technologies: This topic provides students with the skills necessary to analyze, process, and use textual materials for pedagogical purposes. It can be useful in the process of creating pedagogical software tools; however, focusing only on textual materials is not sufficient for developing broader competencies in this field.
2. Technologies for working with presentations: This topic is related to creating presentation materials and organizing effective presentations, providing knowledge about visual and interactive elements necessary for developing pedagogical software tools. Knowing how to use presentations effectively in the educational process is also important.
3. Computer graphics: Knowledge of the basics of computer graphics is essential for designing pedagogical software tools, as visual materials and graphic design simplify students' active learning processes. This area develops skills and competencies useful for designing pedagogical software tools.
4. Technology for creating professional interactive infographics: Competence in creating interactive infographics plays an important role in making pedagogical software tools effective and engaging. This topic enables students to create interactive learning materials and apply them in the educational process.

5. Use of mobile technologies in professional activities: Knowledge about integrating mobile technologies into the educational process ensures more interactive and flexible learning. It also provides the skills necessary to adapt pedagogical software tools for mobile devices.
6. Distance learning technologies and LMS: Working with distance learning systems and Learning Management Systems (LMS) plays an important role in designing pedagogical software tools. Understanding distance learning and LMS helps students organize education effectively in an online format.
7. Use of pedagogical software tools in professional activities: This topic is directly related to the development and practical application of pedagogical software tools and provides students with essential skills for designing educational software. It constitutes the core component of competence.
8. Technology for creating video content: Creating video materials helps make pedagogical software tools more effective and engaging. This topic teaches students how to create video materials and apply them in the educational process.
9. Cloud technologies: Cloud technologies serve as effective tools for storing educational materials, providing access to them, and managing the educational process. They can be applied in the development of pedagogical software tools.
10. Artificial intelligence systems: Artificial intelligence technologies help individualize education, assess students' learning levels, and adapt educational materials. This field is essential for making pedagogical software tools more advanced.

Conclusion and Recommendations. In conclusion, the existing pedagogical problems in developing higher education students' competence in designing pedagogical software tools have been addressed. Through designing pedagogical software tools, students are able to use their free time productively and successfully develop educational software tools relevant to the learning process.

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